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DiscardLess

Strategies for the gradual elimination of discards in European fisheries

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Main Authors: Jordan Feekings (DTU Aqua, Beneficiary 1)

WP Leader: Barry O'Neill

DTU Aqua (Beneficiary 1)

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Role	Name	Organisation	Date
Main Author	Jordan Feekings	DTU Aqua	02/03/2018
WP leader	Barry O'Neill	DTU Aqua	02/03/2018
Coordinator	Clara Ulrich	DTU Aqua	02/03/2018

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Report Highlights

- RTM camera systems are currently far too expensive for the average fisherman.
- The investment risk currently does not outweigh the return.
- Their needs to be done more to document the actual return such systems can bring to the fishermen
- Low light conditions and in murky waters occur in many demersal fisheries which may reduce their applicability in these fisheries.

The methods/approaches followed:

- Workshop.
- Information leaflet.
- Questionnaire.

How these results can be used and by who?

- The results from this work were incorporated into a successful Horizon 2020 application on the use of new and existing technologies in fisheries: SMARTFISH, Smart fisheries technologies for an efficient, compliant and environmentally friendly fishing sector. The project aims to develop, test and promote a suite of high-tech systems for use by the fishing sector across the EU that will enable the sector to optimise its resource efficiency, to improve automatic data collection for fish stock assessment and to provide evidence of compliance with fishery regulations.

Introduction

The main objective of this work package has been to establish the current level of knowledge within the fishing sector on the uses of different real-time monitoring (RTM) and delayed camera systems, their applicability to different fisheries, as well as the feasibility of installing these systems on fishing vessels.

Originally it was proposed to make these tools visible to the fishers through joint participation of representatives from the companies developing trawl based camera systems and fishers at the project kick-off event which was held in Bologne-sur-Mer, France. However, it was not logistically possible or realistic to have fishers from multiple countries and fisheries attend such a workshop. Therefore, to obtain as wide an outreach as possible (i.e. reach as many fishermen as possible) it was decided that the main form of information dissemination would be to create an information leaflet and questionnaire, as opposed to hold a workshop where only a few fishers from a few specific countries and fisheries would be able to participate. The survey (Annex 1) aimed to collate the different trawl-based camera systems and their specifications into one document which could be distributed to different fisheries organisations around Europe. Additionally, a national workshop focusing on fishing gear selectivity and technologies to improve selectivity was held together with Danish fishermen and Danish fishing industry representatives.

Extensive background research was performed, as well as the international network of fishing gear technologists (ICES-FAO Working Group on Fishing Technology and Fish Behaviour) consulted, to discover how many companies are developing real-time monitoring (RTM) and delayed camera systems. The different companies working specifically with camera systems for fishing were contacted and provided with the opportunity to contribute to the information leaflet and questionnaire. Companies which were consulted and contributed to the information leaflet include Trawl camera, Seatronics, Scantrol, SIMRAD, StarOddi, SubC Imaging, and LH camera.

Background

RTM camera systems enable (i) real-time monitoring of the availability of demersal species in the pre-catching phase, (ii) real-time monitoring of all species and size compositions entering the gear during trawling, (iii) real time monitoring of benthic habitats and fauna and (iv) fishery independent assessment of demersal species abundance.

RTM camera systems allow skippers to modify their short term fishing tactics in response to (i) the availability of target species, (ii) the relative abundance of target and non-target species being caught and (iii) the habitat being fished. Vessel operators will therefore be able to make informed decisions that will improve the efficiency of fishing while reducing its impacts. RTM camera systems also allow for monitoring of the seabed and associated benthic fauna and enable improved and more

efficient fishery independent monitoring of demersal species. Furthermore, RTM camera systems can be used to monitor the performance of the gear (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HUE2sWFBgyU>) and observe how small changes affect the selectivity of the gear, as well as observe when the codend is full.

Findings

A total of 8 camera systems, which have been developed directly for the fishing industry or used by the industry were found (Annex 1). Of these systems, 7 were capable of real-time monitoring, while one (GoPro) was only capable of delayed monitoring (i.e. the recordings are only able to be viewed when the camera is retrieved). Four of the camera systems, SubC Imaging (Figure 1), SIMRAD (Figure 2), Seatronics (Figure 3), and LH camera (Figure 4) are tethered camera systems which require a cable to live-stream footage. The camera systems developed by TrawlCamera (Figure 5) are autonomous systems which are capable of both delayed and real-time monitoring. The transmission of still images occurs in real-time via a system of modems, while the video footage can first be viewed when the camera is retrieved.

Figure 1. SubC Imaging's Traw1Cam.

Figure 2. SIMRAD's FX80 camera system.

Figure 3. Seatronics TrawlCAM.

Figure 4. LH camera's trawl camera.

Figure 5. Trawl Camera's Deepwater (left) and Live (right) camera systems.

Two of the systems, Star Oddi's Fish Selector (Figure 6 & 7) and Scantrol's DeepVision (Figure 8), have been developed to not only monitor what is occurring at the seabed but also to be able to length measure the catch entering the trawl. Furthermore, the Fish Selector aims to sort out species and sizes not intended for landing by directing them through a bypass gate (Figure 7). The Fish Selector is placed in front of the cod-end and as the fish swim through the device it is pre-programmed to select fish by specific size and species so those that are not intended for landing, are sorted out and directed away through a bypass gate (Figure 3).

Figure 6. Star Oddi's Fish Selector.

Figure 7. A schematic drawing of the Fish Selector.

Figure 8. Scantrol's DeepVision.

The information leaflet and questionnaire was formulated in both English and Danish and given to the national fisheries organisations in Scotland and Denmark to disseminate amongst its members. Despite these being widely disseminated, no completed questionnaires were received from either country. Therefore, to obtain the Danish fishing industry's perception on camera systems, a workshop was organised in Hirtshals, Denmark on the 1st June 2017. The workshop, organised by DTU Aqua and the Danish fishermen organisation, aimed to i) identify current problems in the different fisheries and how these can be addressed through technical developments, ii) how adequate documentation can be obtained to get new gears implemented in legislation, and iii) present and discuss future technologies and their potential for developing more efficient and selective fisheries under the landing obligation.

The different RTM camera systems and delayed camera systems were presented to fishermen and fisheries representatives from the Danish fishermen organisation (Annex 2) and followed by a discussion around their potential in the different fisheries. The general consensus was that these RTM camera systems are currently far too expensive for the average fisherman, with a system costing typically around 100 000 euros and up. Despite those present agreeing that the added benefits these systems could bring was substantial, they all felt that the risk currently does not outweigh the return. I.e. that their needs to be done more to document the actual return such systems can bring to the fishermen. By having an estimate on what extent these RTM camera systems can increase catch rates, reduce time spent searching for target species etc. the fishermen could gauge the systems potential in their fishery.

One of the limiting factors regarding the applicability of RTM camera systems in demersal fisheries is that they typically take place under low light conditions and in murky waters due to the resuspension of sediment by the trawl doors and ground gear.

Several of the fishermen present mentioned that they were playing around with mounting delayed camera systems (e.g. GoPro) on their gear to observe its performance and modifications they had made. This helps to reaffirm that there is an interest amongst fishermen to better understand what is occurring before and during the capture process but the technologies current available, their associated costs, as well as knowledge around their benefits is currently lacking.

Conclusions

Feedback from fishermen and fisheries representative with Denmark showed that there are still some limiting factors which are inhibiting the uptake of RTM camera technologies, namely their cost, the benefits which can be obtained and their suitability within different fisheries.

To further facilitate the development of RTM camera systems, and obtain the necessary documentation on their benefits, a consortium was assembled in 2017 and funding through the Horizon 2020 programme obtained. SMARTFISH¹, Smart fisheries technologies for an efficient, compliant and environmentally friendly fishing sector, aims to develop, test and promote a suite of high-tech systems for use by the fishing sector across the EU that will enable the sector to optimise its resource efficiency, to improve automatic data collection for fish stock assessment and to provide evidence of compliance with fishery regulations. The project started at the beginning of 2018. One work package in the project SMARTFISH, led by DTU Aqua, aims to make use of underwater camera technologies and automatic image analysis techniques, to enable real-time monitoring (RTM) of the abundance of marine organisms. The objective of the work package is to develop an affordable RTM camera system which can be mounted on trawls, autonomous underwater vehicles (AUV) and towed sledges and apply it to fish-finding, catching, management, stock assessment and habitat mapping. Additionally, the work package incorporates new 3D camera technology (e.g. time of flight) to improve image quality in turbid waters, one of the shortcomings of current RTM camera systems.

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¹https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/212401_en.html

Annex 1. Information leaflet and questionnaire on real-time monitoring camera systems and delayed camera systems.

Enhancing the capacity of fishers to observe what is happening in the gear and make real-time decisions

Name:

Vessel ID:

Fishery (e.g. demersal trawl fishery):

Fishing ground / waters:

Target species (e.g. **Single species fishery**: Nephrops; shrimp; cod **Mixed fishery**: Nephrops and cod; plaice, cod and Nephrops; etc.)

Date:

Background

Several companies are developing camera solutions to monitor what is happening in the gear. These tools provide the possibility to observe what is entering the gear, allowing fishermen the chance to make a range of decisions which have the potential to improve their economy. Camera solutions can be used to:

1. Monitor catches in real time, providing the opportunity to reduce the capture of species or sizes for which no quota is available, an issue of increased importance under the Landing Obligation.
2. Gain a better understanding of where cleaner catches occur
3. Monitor the performance of the gear (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HUe2sWFBgyU>)
4. Observe how small changes affect the selectivity of the gear
5. Know when the codend is full

The following document collates the different tools which are available to monitor catches, both in real-time and delayed. The attached questionnaire aims to ascertain whether there is interest in using these camera solutions to optimize catches and why the uptake of these solutions has been minimal.

Available camera solutions

Below is a list of the different solutions which are available to observe what is happening in the gear. These include camera setups which enable observations in real time as well as systems which allow the downloading of the video footage once the gear is retrieved. The list below includes the websites of the companies as well as video links where you can see the camera systems in action.

Table 1. A list of camera systems currently available, the companies contact details, and if available, videos of the systems.

Company	Camera system	Website/ Brochure	Videos
Trawl camera	Deepwater/Live	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://trawlcamera.com/ http://trawlcamera.com/1trawlcam/files/2011/03/Trawlcam_produktark UK 2014 web.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LioReF5FFu4
Seatronics	TrawlCAM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://seatronics-group.com/equipment-sales/fishing/rawl-mounted-camera-systems/seatronics-trawlcam/ http://trawlcam.com/brochure.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">
Scantrol	DeepVision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://www.scantrol.com/deepvision-subsea-stereo-computer-vision http://www.scantrol.com/wp-content/uploads/2011/05/20150520-Deep-Vision-brochure.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y_x0XADsWdA
SIMRAD	FX80 underwater video camera	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://www.simrad.com/ http://www.simrad.com/www/01/NOKBG0397.nsf/AllWeb/AF7EB33683D62684C1257C2200281969/\$file/367462aa_fx80_data_sheet_english.pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wzxW3P0G0sM https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B8ZCgjtQM3U
StarOddi	Fish Selector	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> http://www.star-oddi.com/products/45/fish-sorter/default.aspx 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g4uoZjFqh8E

SubC Imaging	Traw1Cam	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://subcimaging.com/product/trawl-cam/ • http://subcimaging.com/datasheets/Traw1Cam.pdf 	•
LH camera	LH camera	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://lh-camera.dk/produkter/videokamera/hd-undervandskamera/ 	•
GoPro	Hero 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • http://gopro.com/ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TbQIY247ISk • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xofFvIvEkqM

Table 2. Specifications for the different real-time/delayed decision making tools, their costs, as well as the pros and cons of each systems.

Company	Cost	Data transfer method	Real-time/Delayed	Filming duration	Depth range	Pros	Cons
Trawl camera	723,554 DKK 97,000 (EUR)	Autonomous	Real-time/Delayed	Entire haul (up to 48 hrs)	2000 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cableless camera system • Up to 48 hrs recording • Depth range 	•
Seatronics		Cable	Real-time	Entire haul	1200 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated lights (4*430 lumens) 	•
Scantrol	1,1-1,5 mDKK 150-200,000 (EUR)	Cable	Real-time	Entire haul	2000 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depth range • Integrated lights (2*18600 lumens) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Size (L: 1,5m, W: 1,2m, H: 1m)
SIMRAD	500.000-1 million DKK \$78,000-\$145,00	Cable	Real-time	Entire haul	1800 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated lighting • Can accommodate 	•

	0 (USD)					additional sensors, including Trawl Sonar	
StarOddi	900,000-1,4 million DKK	Cable/ Autonomou s	Real-time	Entire haul/ 4 hours	600 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Additional sensors (temp, depth, inclination) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Size (L: 1,8m, Ø 65 cm)
SubC Imaging	281,086 DKK 40,524 (USD)	Cable/ None	Real-time/ Delayed	Entire haul	500 m 3000 m (optional)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adjustable camera angle Both real-time and delayed footage Integrated lights Integrated Reference Lasers Modular design: each component; camera, light and battery can be used separately HD video and true digital stills (up 24mp) recorded to the camera 	
LH camera	19,995 DKK	Cable/ None	Real-time/ Delayed	Entire haul/ 8-10 hours	200 m	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simplicity (Plug and Play) Price Possibility for analogue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No integrated lighting

						<p>output to the surface.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can accommodate additional sensors 	
GoPro	3,000 DKK	None	Delayed	3-4 hours	40 m (deep-water housing 2600m)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price • Large range of extras (deep-water housing) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depth range • Battery duration

Questionnaire

1. How many of the systems presented in table 1 had you heard of before? **(Please specify which systems)**

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-4
- 5-6
- 7-8

2. What do you perceive are the benefits of using cameras? **(More than one answer can be given)**

- None
- Reduce catches of species for which I have no quota for
- Reduce catches of smaller individuals
- Provide me with a better understanding of where I can get clean catches
- Allow me to continue fishing until the codend is full
- Allow me to monitor gear performance
- Allow me to observe how small changes to my gear affect the selectivity of the gear
- Other (Please specify)

3. Why do you think the general uptake of these technologies is low? **(More than one answer can be given)**

- Expensive
 - No need for them
 - They don't work
 - Extra work
 - Dangerous. Extra cables on the deck
 - Didn't know they existed
 - Other (Please specify)
-

4. Why don't you use these technologies? **(More than one answer can be given)**

- They don't work in my fishery
 - Expensive
 - No need for them
 - They don't work
 - Extra work
 - Dangerous. Extra cables on the deck
 - Didn't know they existed
 - Other (Please specify)
-

5. Which tool do you perceive as the most attractive?

6. Why do you perceive this tool as the most attractive? **(More than one answer can be given)**

- Price
 - Ease of use
 - Best image quality
 - Possibility of adding more than one camera
 - I already use other equipment from this company
 - Other (Please specify)
-

7. Are you interested in knowing more about these technologies?

- Yes No

8. If provided the opportunity, would you be interested in seeing these technologies in use?

- Yes No

9. Are there any additional sensors which may be beneficial to have installed **(More than one answer can be given)**

- Depth
 - Temperature
 - Salinity
 - Turbidity
 - Light intensity
 - Other (Please specify)
-

Annex 2. Presentation for the Danish fishing industry on future technologies and their potential.

Teknologier

- GUDP-VIND
- Lys i trawlet
- Kamera systemer til undervands observationer
- Vores arbejder med undervands kamera til fiskeriet

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- Overvåge fangster i realtid
- Opnå en bedre forståelse for hvornår rene fangster forekommer
- Overvåge hvordan redskabet opføre sig
- Observere hvordan små ændringer kan påvirke selektiviteten
- Se hvornår posen er fyldt

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- TrawlCamera
 - Trådløst kamera system
 - Optage i realtid/ forsinket
 - ~ 48 timers film
 - Maks dybde 2000 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Pris ~750 000 DKK

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- Simrad FX80
 - Kablet kamera system
 - Optage i realtid
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 1800 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Påmonteres flere sensorer inklusiv trawl sonar
 - Pris ~500 000-1m DKK

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- SubC Imaging
 - Kablet kamera system
 - Optage i realtid
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 6000 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Justbar kameravinkel
 - Pris ~300 000 DKK

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- Seatronics TrawlCam
 - Kablet kamera system
 - Optage i realtid
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 1200 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Pris ?

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- Scantrol DeepVision
 - Kablet kamera system
 - Optage i realtid
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 2000 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Pris ~1,1-1,5m DKK
 - Meget stor (1,5m)

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- StarOddi – Fish Selector
 - Kablet kamera system
 - Optage i realtid
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 600 m
 - Integreret lys
 - Flere sensorer
 - Pris ~1,0-1,4m DKK
 - Meget stor (1,8m)

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- LH Kamera
 - Kablet/stand-alone kamera system
 - Optage i realtid/ forsinket
 - Filme hele træk
 - Maks dybde 200-500 m
 - Flere sensorer
 - Pris ~20 000 DKK (Kun kamera)

Kamera systemer til fiskeriet

- GoPro
 - Kablet/stand-alone kamera system
 - Filme 3-4 timer
 - Maks dybde 40-60 m (300m)
 - Pris ~4 000 DKK (Kun kamera)

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